

Coordination complexes of Schiff base ligand : 5-Diethylamino 2-thiazole 2-yliminomethyl phenol with Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} ions; phenoxazinone synthase like activity of Cu^{II} complex

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Abstract : A new Schiff base ligand, 5-diethylamino 2-thiazole 2-yliminomethyl phenol (HL) has been synthesized by condensation of 2-aminothiazole with 4-diethylaminosalicylaldehyde. A series of complexes of first row transition metal ions (Cu²⁺, Mn²⁺, Co²⁺ and Ni²⁺) with the ligand are reported here. The ligand and the metal complexes have been characterized through spectroscopic techniques e.g. NMR, ESIMS, FTIR, UV-Vis spectroscopy; elemental analysis, cyclic voltammetry and differential pulse voltammetry. The reported Cu^{II} complex were examined *in vitro* for the catalytic oxidation of 2-aminophenol to 2-aminophenoxazine-3-one. The catalytic activity of complex was investigated with UV-Vis spectrophotometry in MeOH medium. Kinetic parameters for the catalytic activity of the complexes are as follows : $V_{\max} = 1.2 \times 10^{-8} \text{ M s}^{-1}$, $K_{\text{cat}} = 4.3 \text{ h}^{-1}$, $K_M = 3.304 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M}$.

Keywords : Schiff base, cyclic voltammetry, UV-Vis spectrophotometry, 2-aminophenol, 2-aminophenoxazine-3-one.

Introduction

Different types of Schiff base ligands and their transition metal complexes have been widely studied for biological¹⁻⁴, material⁵⁻⁸ and industrial^{9,10} application. Nature has designed many metalloenzymes that activate molecular oxygen for specific biological oxidation reactions. The oxidation of molecular oxygen under mild aerobic condition is of great interest for researchers due to their industrial¹¹ and synthetic¹² applications. Copper is a physiologically essential element and exhibits amazing activity in different biological catalysis¹³. Metalloenzymes which activate molecular oxygen consist mainly copper, iron or manganese at the active sites. Because of its biological relevance, a large number of copper(II) complexes have been synthesized and explored as model systems in bio-inorganic chemistry¹⁴. One of the important metalloenzyme that utilize molecular oxygen for biological oxidation process is a phenoxazinone synthase^{15,16a,b,17}.

The enzyme phenoxazinone synthase, a multi copper oxidase is found in the bacterium *Streptomyces antibioticus* and catalyzes the oxidative coupling of wide variety of

substituted *o*-amino phenol to phenoxazinone chromophore. Phenoxazinone synthase is involved in the final step of the biosynthesis of actinomycin D¹⁸ and used clinically for the treatment of certain type of tumors¹⁹. Phenoxazinone synthase possesses a unique characteristics. Usually multicopper oxidases catalyze one electron oxidation process, but phenoxazinone synthase catalyses two electron oxidation. Oxidative coupling of two molecules of *o*-amino phenol involves total six electron oxidation consisting of three successive two electron oxidation processes^{16a,b}.

However model complexes of phenoxazinone synthase is very limited with copper. Speier *et al.* used several salts of Cu e.g. CuCl, CuCl₂, CuSO₄, Cu(NO₃)₂, Cu(OAc)₂, Cu(OCH₃)₂ and Cu(OCH₃)(Cl) as catalysts for the oxidation of *o*-aminophenol with dioxygen which showed that strongly coordinating N-donor ligands have a higher rate of reaction²⁰. Halligudi *et al.* reported a Cu complex of bis(2-hydroxyethylbenzimidazol) anchored to a chloromethylated polystyrene for *o*-amino phenol oxidation. The study revealed that the anchored complex had higher rate than the unattached complex²¹. Chowdhuri

et al. reported a tetranuclear Cu_4O_4 cubane as the model complex with a redox non-innocent imino-phenol ligand with detail spectro-electrochemical study. This is the most close model to the natural system so far²². Banu *et al.* reported a phenoxo bridged Cu complex with high phenoxazinone synthase activity. They also mentioned that the higher activity for such complexes might be due to the intrinsic nature of the ligand^{23a,b}. The other transition metal complexes showing phenoxazinone synthase activity are cobalt^{24b,c,e,f} and manganese^{24a,d,25,26}. In such type of catalytic reaction TEMPO (2,2,6,6-tetramethyl-1-piperidinyloxy)²⁷ free radical is used as an initiator.

In this paper we have synthesized a series of complexes of Mn^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} and Cu^{2+} with the ligand (5-diethylamino 2-thiazole 2-yliminomethyl phenol) and studied their activity for the oxidation of *o*-aminophenol. Phenoxazinone synthase activity were checked in methanol for all the complexes by monitoring the evolution of UV-Vis spectral band at 430 nm, characteristics of phenoxazinone chromophore. However, among all of them only Cu^{2+} complex shows phenoxazinone synthase like activity. Kinetic data has been determined by UV-Vis spectroscopic method.

Experimental

Materials :

All the reagents (2-aminothiazole and 4-diethylsalicylaldehyde) used for the synthesis of ligand were purchased from Aldrich and used without further purification. The HPLC grade solvents used for electrochemical and spectral analysis were purchased from Spectrochem. All metal perchlorate salts used in this study were prepared in laboratory according to the published procedure²⁸⁻³⁰.

Physical measurements :

Infrared (IR) spectra were recorded on IR prestige²¹, Shimadzu Infrared Spectrophotometer between 400 cm^{-1} to 4000 cm^{-1} in KBr pellet. UV-Vis spectra were recorded in Perkin-Elmer (Lambda-750) UV-Vis/NIR spectrophotometer. Thermogram was recorded on DTG-60, Shimadzu-Japan, TG/DT analyser in temperature range of 25 to $1000\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. TGA analysis was done in platinum

cell under nitrogen atmosphere, heating rate was between $10\text{ }^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$ to $1000\text{ }^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$. ^1H NMR spectra of ligand were recorded using a Bruker Advance DPX-400 NMR spectrometer. ESI-MS analysis data were obtained by using Jeol JMS-700 spectrometer. Cyclic voltammogram was recorded in CHI6003E Potentiostat in a typical three electrode system : Pt or glassy carbon working electrode, Ag/AgCl reference electrode and Pt-counter electrode. TEAP used as supporting electrolyte in cyclic volumetric study was prepared according to literature³¹.

Synthesis of ligand (HL) :

The Schiff base ligand was prepared by the condensation of 2-aminothiazole with 4-diethylaminosalicylaldehyde in 1 : 1 molar ratio. A mixture of 2-aminothiazole (1500 mg, 15 mmol) and 4-diethylaminosalicylaldehyde (2898.52 mg, 15 mmol) was refluxed in 60 ml MeOH for 7 h at $65\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ temperature in nitrogen atmosphere. A brownish yellow colored solid was obtained. The residue was filtered and washed with ice cold methanol. The solid was then purified through silica column. Pure product was eluted at 35% polarity of dichloromethane in hexane solvent. Crude yield : 40.5%, m.p. $102\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. Elemental analysis for chemical formula Calcd. (%) ($\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{17}\text{N}_3$) : C, 61.06; H, 6.22; N, 15.26. Found (%) : C, 60.09; H, 6.25; N 15.82; ESI-MS : m/z : 276 (M+1); ^1H NMR (δ ppm) (CDCl_3-d_6) : 1.65 (6H, t), 3.43 (4H, q), 7.90 (5H, m), 8.90 (1H, s), 12.67 (1H, s); IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : $\nu(\text{ArC}=\text{C})$ (3105), νCN (1642) $\nu(\text{Alkane-C-H})$ (2973); UV-Vis (MeOH) : $\lambda_{\text{max}}/\text{nm}$ ($\epsilon/\text{M}^{-1}\text{ cm}^{-1}$) : 417 nm (12010.7), 351(sh) (2732.3).

Synthesis of complex :

All the complexes were prepared by similar procedure starting with same amount of the ligand and maintaining similar stoichiometry for the reactants. Detail synthesis of only Cu complex is furnished below :

$[\text{Cu}(\text{L})_2]$ (1) : Ligand HL (552 mg, 2 mmol) was dissolved in 40 mL methanol. Et_3N (0.202 mg, 2 mL) was added to the ligand solution under stirring condition followed by 5 mL methanolic solution of $\text{Cu}(\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (361.93 mg, 1 mmol). The reaction mixture was refluxed for 5 h. Green colored precipitate appeared gradually

with the progress of the reaction. The dark green solid was then filtered under vacuum and washed with cold methanol (3×2 ml). Crude yield : 55.89%, M.W. 615.2, ESI-MS (Jeol-JMS) m/z (% , ion) : 612.5 (CuL₂+2H)⁺. Elemental analysis for chemical formula Calcd. (%) (C₂₈H₃₂N₆O₂SCu) : C, 54.06; H, 5.32; N, 13.76. Found (%) : C, 52.92; H, 5.95; N 12.98; IR (KBr) cm⁻¹ : ν (CN) 1607, ν (Ar-C=C-H) 3099, ν (Alkane C-H) 2967; UV-Vis (λ_{max} , nm) in DMSO : 277(sh) nm (ϵ = 1884), 419 nm (ϵ = 13300), 716 nm (ϵ = 286).

[Co(L)₂] (**2**) : Crude yield : 41.23%. Color of solid precipitate was dark orange. M.W. 608.3, ESI-MS m/z (% , ion) : 608.3 (M+H)⁺. Elemental analysis for chemical formula Calcd. (%) (C₂₈H₃₂N₆O₂SCo) : C, 55.06; H, 5.49; N, 12.76. Found (%) : C, 54.32; H, 5.30; N 12.89; IR (KBr) cm⁻¹ : ν (CN) 1611, ν (Ar-C=C-H) 3095, ν (Alkane C-H) 2970; UV-Vis (λ_{max} /nm) in DMSO : (ϵ /M⁻¹ cm⁻¹) 423 nm (ϵ = 7802.1), 452 nm (ϵ = 5464.3).

[Mn(L)₂] (**3**) : Crude yield : 35.6%, Color of solid precipitate was dark brown. M.W. 605.3, m.p. 220 °C; ESI-MS (Jeol-JMS) m/z (% , ion) : 605.3 (MnL₂+H)⁺. Elemental analysis for chemical formula Calcd. (%) (C₂₈H₃₂N₆O₂SMn) : C, 52.06; H, 5.32; N, 12.76. Found (%) : C, 53.12; H, 5.05; N 11.98; IR (KBr) cm⁻¹ : ν (CN) 1615, ν (Ar-C=C-H) 3089, ν (Alkane C-H) 2945; UV-Vis (λ_{max} , nm) in DCM : 422 nm (ϵ = 7912.1), 347 nm (ϵ = 12841.3), 477 nm (ϵ = 3562.3).

[Ni(L)₂] (**4**) : Crude yield : 45.1%. Brown precipitate was obtained from the reaction mixture. ESI-MS m/z (% , ion) : 607.5 (M+H)⁺. Elemental analysis for chemical formula Calcd. (%) (C₂₈H₃₂N₆O₂SNi) : C, 53.06; H, 5.02; N, 12.67. Found (%) : C, 52.92; H, 4.95; N, 12.95; IR (KBr) cm⁻¹ : ν (CN) 1612, ν (Ar-C=C-H) 3098, ν (Alkane C-H) 2973; UV-Vis (λ_{max} , nm) in DCM : 421 nm (ϵ = 17584), 480(sh) nm (ϵ = 3661).

Results and discussion

Synthesis and characterization :

Synthesis : Synthetic scheme of the ligand and the complexes are given in Fig. 1. The ligand was synthesised by Schiff base condensation of 2-aminothiazole and

4-diethylsalicylaldehyde. After purification by column chromatography in silica with 35% DCM in hexane solvent mixture the yield was 35%. The complexes were prepared under refluxing condition with a reaction mixture of metal perchlorate salts, ligand and triethyl amine in 1 : 2 : 2 ratio.

Fig. 1. Molecular structure of complex.

Spectroscopic characterization :

In IR spectra ligand and complexes showed all the characteristic stretching frequency. One such prominent band in ligand appears around 3105 cm⁻¹ which is also observed in complexes. This strong band may be assigned to Ar-C=C stretching. Another sharp band appear in the ligand at 1642 cm⁻¹ due to (C=N) stretching which is shifted to lower energy region in all the metal complexes. This shifting of C=N stretching frequency towards higher wavelength indicates the coordination of imine-N to the metals.

The electronic spectrum of ligand shows one intense band at 417 nm. This transition was also observed in all metal complexes with a slight red shift (Complex **1** : 419 nm, Complex **2** : 423 nm, Complex **3** : 422 nm, Complex **4** : 421 nm)³². This transition may be assigned as intraligand transition. Comparison of the spectra of ligand with metal complexes is displayed in Fig. 2. The band at 417 nm clearly showed a red shift upon complexation with the metals which resemble a donor-acceptor trend in metal complexes of Schiff base³³. In complexes there is a shoulder in the region 462–475 nm (Complex **1** : 462 nm,

Complex **3** : 475 nm, Complex **4** : 474 nm). According to literature this shoulder may be due to transition from phenolate-O to $M(II)^{34a}$. In Mn-complex one additional band appear at higher energy region which may be due to $\pi-\pi^*$ transition which takes place in azomethene moiety of the ligand^{34b,c,d,e}. In the low energy at high concentration region complex **1** shows one metal based transition at 716 nm which can be assigned as a d-d band in the Cu complex³⁵.

Electrochemical analysis :

Cyclic voltammetry of complexes were investigated in Pt-working electrode containing 0.1 M TEAP as supporting electrolyte in DMSO. The cyclic voltammogram was taken on a potential range of -1.5 V to 1.0 V, at 100 mV s⁻¹. Ferrocene was used as an internal standard, and the potentials are referred versus the ferrocenium/ferrocene (Fc^+/Fc) couple. In the anodic scan complex **1** showed one irreversible oxidation peak at 0.7 V which may be assigned as phenoxide to phenoxyl radical oxidation. Although not well resolved, this oxidation process is also observed in other complexes. Complex **2**, **3**, **4** displays this peak at 0.65 V, 0.80 V and 0.86 V respectively. In the negative side complex **1** displays one irreversible peak at -0.72 V, which can be assigned as $Cu^{II/I}$ reduction process. In addition one quasi-reversible peak was ob-

served at -1.3 V ($\Delta E_p = 300$ mV) which may be due to ligand based reduction (Fig. 3). This is most probably the reduction of the imine functionality in the ligand producing corresponding amine with a fair stability which shows the irreversible to quasi-reversible nature of the peak³⁶. This ligand based reduction is also observed in other complexes at -1.74 V, -1.73 V and -1.55 V for complex **2**, **3** and **4** respectively (Figs. S9-S14). Complex **2** shows $Co^{III/II}$ reduction on the negative scan at -0.11 V. Complex **3** has a metal based oxidation corresponding to the $Mn^{II/III}$ couple at 0.53 V. Similarly complex **4** shows $Ni^{II/III}$ oxidation at 0.63 V and $Ni^{III/I}$ reduction at -0.13 V respectively.

Magnetic susceptibility measurement :

The magnetic moment (μ_{eff}) values for all the complexes with ligand (HL) are provided in Table 3. For the Cu^{II} complex, μ_{eff} value is 1.75 BM corresponds to one unpaired electron present in complex **1**. μ_{eff} for Co^{II} complex is 3.62 suggesting three unpaired electrons are present in complex **2**. The μ_{eff} value of Mn^{II} complex and Ni^{II} are 5.63 and 2.82 respectively, suggested that complex **3** has five unpaired electron and complex **4** has 2 unpaired electrons. The magnetic moment value confirmed, all the complexes are high spin and may be tetrahedral in nature.

Fig. 2. (a) Relative electronic spectra of HL, complex **1**, **2**, **3** and **4**, (b) Electronic spectra of complex **1**, Inset : d-d band in complex **1**.

Kinetic study of the oxidation of o-amino phenol :

Catalytic performance for the phenoxazinone synthase like activity were performed with all the complexes reported in this manuscript, but only complex 1 shows catalytic activity and the rests are non-responsive.

The phenoxazinone synthase like activity was performed in catalytic amount of complex 1 (1.0×10^{-5}) with substrate *o*-aminophenol (100 eq) in methanol medium at 25 °C in aerobic condition. The kinetic study was carried out spectrophotometrically by monitoring the absorbance peak at 430 nm, which is characteristic for phenoxazinone chromophore. For this typical experiment, 2 mL methanolic solution of complex 1 was taken in quartz cell and externally 100 eq of substrate solution was added to the cell. The investigation was then followed by UV-Vis spectral scan at the interval of every 15 min upto 6 h. Progress of the reaction was examined by monitoring the development of peak at 430 nm in electronic spectra as a function with time (Fig. 4). Furthermore, to find out the rate dependency a set of experiments were performed with varying amount of substrate concentration at a fixed concentration of catalyst. The rate of reaction was calculated by initial rate method and the result was evaluated by Lineweaver-Burk plot (Fig. 5).

Fig. 3. Cyclic voltammograms of compound in Pt-working electrode. Complex 1; scan rate V : 100 mV s⁻¹.

Table 1. Redox potential of metal complexes were determined under nitrogen atmosphere in DMSO solvent

Complexes	$E_{(ox)}$ [vs Ag/AgCl]	$E_{(red)}$ [vs Ag/AgCl]
1	0.72 ^(ir)	-0.7 ^(ir) , -1.23 V ^(qr)
2	0.653 V ^(ir)	-0.11 V ^(ir) , -1.74 V ^(qr)
3	0.53 V ^(ir) , 0.8 V ^(ir)	-1.73 V ^(qr)
4	0.66 ^(ir) , 0.86 ^(ir)	-0.12V ^(ir) , -1.55 V ^(qr)

^{ir}Irreversible, ^{qr}Quasi-reversible.

This type of rate dependency on the substrate concentration may be explained by Michaelis-Menten equation for enzyme kinetics. The enzyme kinetics leads to well known Michaelis-Menten equation.

$$V = V_{max} [S]/K_M + [S]$$

where V = initial rate; $[S]$ = concentration of the substrate (*o*-aminophenol); K_M = Michaelies-Menten constant for the metal complex; V_{max} = maximum initial rate. Lineweaver-Burk equation is one of the most widely used equation through which Michaelies-Menten equation can be transformed to algebraic form. By applying this method K_M and V_{max} can be calculated. The turn over

Table 2. Kinetic parameter for the active complex

Complex	K_{cat} (h ⁻¹)	K_M (M)	V_{max} (M s ⁻¹)
1	4.3	3.304×10^{-4}	1.2×10^{-8}

Fig. 4. Increase in absorbance at around 430 nm after the addition of 100 eq *o*-amino phenol to 10^{-5} M concentration of complex 1. The electronic spectra were recorded at the interval of every 15 min.

Fig. 5. Rate vs substrate concentration plot for the oxidation of *o*-aminophenol in methanol catalyzed by the complex at 25 °C. Lineweaver-Burk plot for the oxidation of *o*-aminophenol.

Table 3. Magnetic moment (μ_{eff})

Complex	μ_{eff} (BM) ^a
1 Cu(L ₂)	1.75
2 Co(L ₂)	3.62
3 Mn(L ₂)	5.63
4 Ni(L ₂)	2.82

BM = Bohr Magneton.

number (TON) of the complex K_{cat} can be obtained by dividing the value of V_{max} with the concentration of complex. The concentration of phenoxazone chromophore was calculated on the basis of its molar extinction coefficient in methanol ($\epsilon_{430} = 9095 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) at 430 nm³⁷.

Thermogravimetric analysis :

Thermogravimetry analysis (TGA) showed that the complex (1) starts the decomposition of thiazole moiety (present in ligand HL) at 270 °C and finished at 370 °C. The observed loss of weight is 32%, almost similar with the calculated value of two thiazole rings (32.8%)³⁸. Again there is another loss in weight of 54.8% in the temperature range 505–700 °C, which matches with the calculated value of rest part of ligand (HL) 56.2%. This loss may be due to the decomposition of the remaining ligand present in metal complex.

Fig. 6. TGA curve for complex (1).

Conclusion

Synthesis and spectroscopic characterization of Mn, Co, Ni and Cu complexes of the Schiff base ligand, 5-diethylamino 2-thiazole 2-yliminomethyl phenol are reported here. Cu complex has also been characterized by single crystal X-ray crystallography. Phenoxazinone synthase is a naturally occurring polynuclear Cu catalyst. With respect to the other metalloenzymes biomimetic study of phenoxazinone synthase is less explored. In addition to

copper, manganese and cobalt complexes also exhibit this activity. Biomimetic study for phenoxazinone synthase like activity have been carried out for all the complexes reported in this study. However the results shows that only the copper complex has phenoxazinone synthase like activity. Moderate rate for the catalysis may be due to the mononuclear nature of the copper complex. However the ligand used here is a Schiff base which can be synthesized very easily. Now we are trying to develop a new ligand system with bridging sides which can provide a similar donor environment to the metal ions as in the active site of the phenoxazinone synthase.

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Supplementary data

Supplementary material contains the following items : Mass spectra of ligand, ¹H NMR spectra of ligand, mass spectra of complexes, FTIR spectra of ligand compared with complexes, cyclic voltammogram of complexes.

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